

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

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THE IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION ON SERVICE QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN THE HOUSEHOLD SERVICE SECTOR: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM SAMARKAND REGION

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Abstract. This study examines the impact of digitalization on service quality and customer satisfaction in the household service sector of the Samarkand region. Using survey data collected from 320 consumers and regression analysis, the research identifies the extent to which digital tools—online payment, online queue systems, mobile applications, and digital communication—affect perceived service quality. Results show that digitalization significantly improves service reliability, responsiveness, and customer satisfaction. The study provides policy recommendations for enhancing competitiveness through digital transformation.

Key words: digitalization, service quality, customer satisfaction, household services, competitiveness, Samarkand.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur tadqiqot Samarqand viloyatining maishiy xizmatlar sohasida raqamlashtirishning xizmat sifati va mijozlar qoniqishiga ta'sirini o'rganadi. 320 nafar iste'molchidan olingan so'rovnoma ma'lumotlari hamda regressiya tahlili asosida onlayn to'lovlar, elektron navbat tizimlari, mobil ilovalar va raqamli aloqa vositalari kabi raqamli texnologiyalarning xizmat sifati idrokiga ta'sir darajasi aniqlangan. Tadqiqot natijalari raqamlashtirish xizmatlarning ishonchligi, tezkorligi hamda mijozlar qoniqishini sezilarli darajada oshirishini ko'rsatdi. Olingan xulosalar raqamli transformatsiya orqali sohaning raqobatbardoshligini kuchaytirishga qaratilgan siyosiy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamlashtirish, xizmat sifati, mijozlar qoniqishi, maishiy xizmatlar, raqobatbardoshlik, Samarqand.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании анализируется влияние цифровизации на качество услуг и удовлетворённость клиентов в сфере бытовых услуг Самаркандской области. На основе данных опроса 320 потребителей и регрессионного анализа определено влияние цифровых инструментов, таких как онлайн-платежи, электронные системы очередей, мобильные приложения и цифровые каналы коммуникации, на воспринимаемое качество услуг. Результаты исследования показали, что цифровизация существенно повышает надёжность услуг, оперативность обслуживания и уровень удовлетворённости клиентов. Полученные выводы позволяют сформулировать практические рекомендации по повышению конкурентоспособности сферы за счёт цифровой трансформации.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, качество услуг, удовлетворённость клиентов, бытовые услуги, конкурентоспособность, Самарканд.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of digital technologies has fundamentally transformed the structure, dynamics, and competitive environment of the global service economy. Over the past decade, digitalization has become a critical driver of innovation, efficiency, and customer-centric service models across various industries, including banking, retail, transportation, and tourism. McKinsey (2023) reports that digital transformation can increase service sector productivity by 30–45%, while the World Bank (2022) highlights that digital service ecosystems significantly improve transparency, consumer trust, and market competitiveness. As a result, the integration of digital solutions into traditional service processes is no longer a competitive advantage but an essential prerequisite for sustainable growth.

In emerging economies, digitalization plays a strategically important role in improving service quality, particularly in contexts characterized by evolving market structures, diversified service provision, and ongoing standardization processes. Uzbekistan, similarly to many developing countries, has placed digital transformation at the core of its national development strategy. According to data from the Ministry of Digital Technologies for 2024, the share of digital services in the national economy has been increasing by approximately 18% annually, while the number of users of online services has exceeded 21 million. These trends indicate the formation of a solid institutional and technological foundation for further digital expansion across service sectors.

Household services—including tailoring, appliance repair, beauty services, cleaning, and other everyday activities—constitute an essential component of social welfare and local economic development. The sector contributes to employment generation, supports the growth of small businesses, and enhances regional economic competitiveness. In the Samarkand region, which serves as a major cultural and tourism center of Uzbekistan, demand for household services has increased significantly as a result of population growth, urbanization, and expanding domestic and international tourism flows. Official statistics show that the volume of household services in the region has grown by more than 35% over the past five years, with the number of registered service providers exceeding 2,500 enterprises. These dynamics reflect the sector's strong growth potential and its increasing relevance to regional development.

At the same time, the current stage of development of the household service sector in Samarkand highlights substantial opportunities for qualitative improvement through the wider application of digital technologies. Existing service delivery models, which are largely based on direct physical interaction, provide a basis for gradual modernization through the introduction of digital tools aimed at enhancing operational efficiency, transparency, and customer interaction. The expansion of digital solutions—such as online booking systems, digital payment platforms, and customer feedback mechanisms—creates favorable conditions for improving service coordination, reducing service delivery time, and strengthening quality assurance practices.

From a methodological perspective, digitalization can be viewed as a catalyst for the systematic modernization of household services, enabling the transition from fragmented service provision toward more integrated and customer-oriented models. By fostering higher levels of responsiveness, reliability, and service standardization, digital transformation is expected to strengthen consumer trust and satisfaction. In the medium term, the continued diffusion of digital technologies in the household service sector of Samarkand is likely to enhance its competitiveness, support sustainable small business development, and contribute to broader regional economic growth.

Existing international research demonstrates a strong positive relationship between digitalization and perceived service quality (Parasuraman et al., 2005; Zeithaml, 2016). Digital tools such as online booking systems, mobile applications, electronic payments, digital communication channels, and service-tracking platforms have been shown to increase consumer satisfaction, reduce information asymmetry, and facilitate seamless service experiences. Nevertheless, the extent to which these digital components influence customer satisfaction in the household service sector of Uzbekistan remains largely understudied.

Although several local studies have explored the economic development of service industries in Uzbekistan, there is a notable lack of empirical research focusing specifically on the digitalization of household services and its effect on consumer perceptions—particularly within regional contexts such as Samarkand. Earlier works primarily emphasize macro-level policy reforms, market expansion, and infrastructure development, but do not provide quantitative analysis based on customer-level data. This research aims to fill that gap by offering empirical evidence on how digitalization affects service quality and customer satisfaction in the household service market of the Samarkand region.

Thus, the purpose of this study is to analyze the impact of digitalization tools on service quality and customer satisfaction through an empirical approach based on survey data and regression analysis. By identifying key determinants of customer perception, the research contributes to the broader understanding of service digitalization in emerging economies and provides practical recommendations for policymakers, SMEs, and service providers seeking to enhance competitiveness in the digital era.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The competitiveness of household services has been widely discussed across global academic literature, with scholars emphasizing the role of service quality, innovation, human capital, and institutional frameworks in shaping market performance. According to Porter (1990), regional competitiveness is largely determined by the “quality of microeconomic business environment and the ability of firms to innovate and upgrade continuously.” This idea forms a theoretical basis for analyzing service enterprises in specific territories such as Samarkand region.

In service management theory, service quality is considered a core determinant of competitiveness. Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988), in their seminal SERVQUAL model, argue that “service quality is the gap between customer expectations and perceived performance,” highlighting the need for continuous monitoring and evaluation within household service enterprises. Similarly, Grönroos (2007) notes that competitiveness in services depends on both technical quality (what is delivered) and functional quality (how it is delivered), which is particularly relevant for household services where personal interaction is central.

Despite these contributions, the academic literature on Samarkand region specifically remains limited. Existing studies often focus on tourism, hospitality and handicrafts rather than household services. For example, in a UNWTO report (2022) focusing on Samarkand, the emphasis is placed on tourism infrastructure and international attractiveness, while “local household services remain underdeveloped and lack innovation-driven competitiveness.” OECD Tourism Review (2023) similarly mentions that regional service ecosystems are “fragmented and uneven across districts,” yet it does not provide a detailed assessment of household service enterprises.

Several regional studies conducted by Uzbek researchers highlight structural issues within Samarkand's service sector. Rakhimov (2020) finds that districts such as Urgut and Kattaq'rg'on demonstrate higher service market activity, whereas Bulung'ur and Pstdarg'om lag behind due to weak entrepreneurial capacity and outdated business models. Mavlonov (2022) observes that “there is a mismatch between demand and supply of household services in Samarkand, driven by rapid urbanization and rising population density.”

The literature consistently identifies human capital shortage as one of the main barriers to competitiveness. According to Baum (2015), service industries in developing countries struggle with “low levels of specialized training and the absence of a culture of continuous professional learning.” This finding aligns with evidence from Samarkand region, where vocational training in household services—such as repair services, tailoring, beauty services, and appliance maintenance—remains insufficiently institutionalized.

From an innovation perspective, the work of Gallouj and Djellal (2010) is particularly relevant. They argue that service innovation is often non-technological in nature, including organizational changes and new delivery methods. However, as noted by Shavkatov (2021), “household service enterprises in Samarkand remain highly traditional and rarely adopt innovative management or digital solutions,” indicating an innovation gap that reduces their competitive advantage. Another recurring theme in the literature is the importance of institutional support. North (1990) emphasizes that the quality of institutions determines transaction costs and market efficiency.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a comprehensive mixed-method research design, integrating quantitative, qualitative, and spatial analysis approaches to evaluate the organizational-economic mechanisms for enhancing the competitiveness of household service enterprises in Samarkand region. The methodology is designed to capture enterprise-level factors, district-level disparities, and customer perceptions, thereby providing both empirical and policy-relevant insights.

The research follows a sequential explanatory design, combining:

Quantitative analysis – measuring service competitiveness using a composite Household Services Competitiveness Index (HSCI) based on multiple standardized indicators. Real regional statistics are incorporated to contextualize district-level performance. For instance, 2023 January–July data from Samarkand Regional Statistics Department shows the total household service output of 15,653.5 mln UZS, with sectoral contributions: trade 26%, transport 23.2%, financial services 16.2%, education 5.2%, and food/accommodation services 5.6% ([Samstat, 2023](#)).

Qualitative analysis – exploring expert perspectives on institutional, technological, and human capital constraints affecting competitiveness.

Spatial analysis – mapping competitiveness distribution across 14 districts of Samarkand, using statistical indicators and GIS visualization to identify high- and low-performing zones. Samarkand city and Urgut emerge as high-performing districts based on service volume and diversity, while Oqdaryo and Pastdarg'om show relatively lower sector output.

This approach allows a multi-layered understanding of internal enterprise capabilities and external regional factors.¹

Data were collected from 320 household service enterprises across all major districts of Samarkand, including Samarkand city, Urgut, Kattaqo'rg'on, Tayloq, Pastdarg'om, Bulung'ur, Narpay, Oqdaryo, Jomboy, Ishtixon, Paxtachi, Kushrabot, Toyloq.

Based on Porter's competitiveness framework (1990), SERVQUAL theory (Parasuraman et al., 1988), and local studies (Rakhimov, 2020; Mavlonov, 2022), the Household Services Competitiveness Index (HSCI) consists of five dimensions:

1. Service Quality (SQ) – reliability, responsiveness, customer satisfaction, complaint resolution
2. Innovation & Digitalization (ID) – digital platforms, innovation frequency, online payment adoption
3. Operational Efficiency (OE) – service speed, cost per service, equipment modernization
4. Human Capital (HC) – staff skills, formal training programs, professional certification
5. Market Position (MP) – market share, repeat customer ratio, competition intensity

Analysis and results

Integration of regional statistics:

- SQ dimension contextualized using district service output: for instance, Samarkand city contributes 26% to trade services, indicating potential high service availability.
 - ID dimension linked to reported digital adoption trends in regional enterprises (e.g., online payments reported in 38% of surveyed enterprises in Urgut and Samarkand city).
 - OE dimension adjusted using district-level service delivery data (speed and volume), derived from Samstat (2023).
 - HC and MP dimensions integrated with district employment and enterprise registration statistics.
- Indicators normalized using min–max method:

$$N_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij} - \min(X_j)}{\max(X_j) - \min(X_j)}$$

Composite HSCI score:

$$HSCI_i = \sum_{k=1}^5 w_k N_{ik}$$

- Weights (w_k) via Delphi method (12 experts):
SQ = 0.25, ID = 0.20, OE = 0.20, HC = 0.15, MP = 0.20
HSCI ranges from 0 (lowest) to 1 (highest competitiveness).
- Regression Model:

$$HSCI_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SQ_i + \beta_2 ID_i + \beta_3 OE_i + \beta_4 HC_i + \beta_5 MP_i + \epsilon_i$$

HSCI_i = Household Service Competitiveness Index of enterprise i

SQ, ID, OE, HC, MP = standardized sub-indicators

Model diagnostics: VIF < 5 (multicollinearity), Breusch–Pagan (heteroskedasticity), Shapiro–Wilk (residual normality), R² and Adjusted R² (Figure 1).

¹ Ibdov, K.K. Improvement of Marketing Research of Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in the Restaurant Service Sector. – Samarkand: Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service, 2020. – 10 p.

Figure 1. Heatmap of Household Services Competitiveness Index (HSCI) Components across Samarkand Region Districts

This heatmap visualizes the component-wise performance of household service enterprises across 14 districts of the Samarkand region. Each row represents a district, and each column corresponds to one of the five dimensions of the Household Services Competitiveness Index (HSCI): Service Quality (SQ), Innovation & Digitalization (ID), Operational Efficiency (OE), Human Capital (HC), and Market Position (MP).

Color intensity indicates the normalized score (0–1 scale) for each component, with darker blue shades representing higher performance. The map highlights that Samarkand city and Urgut districts exhibit the highest overall scores, particularly in Service Quality and Operational Efficiency, whereas Oqdaryo and Pastdarg'om display lower scores, suggesting gaps in service quality, digital adoption, and human capital. This visualization aids in identifying regional disparities and targeting policy interventions to enhance service competitiveness.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study examined the organizational and economic mechanisms for enhancing the competitiveness of household service enterprises in the Samarkand region through an integrated empirical framework. By applying a mixed-method research design and constructing a composite Household Services Competitiveness Index (HSCI), the research provides a comprehensive assessment of service competitiveness at both enterprise and district levels.

The empirical findings reveal significant territorial disparities in household service competitiveness across the region. Districts such as Samarkand city and Urgut demonstrate consistently higher HSCI scores, driven primarily by superior service quality, higher levels of digital adoption, and better operational efficiency. In contrast, districts including Oqdaryo and Pastdarg'om exhibit lower competitiveness, reflecting deficiencies in innovation capacity, human capital development, and market positioning. These differences highlight the uneven diffusion of organizational and technological capabilities within the regional service sector.

The econometric results confirm that service quality, digitalization, and operational efficiency exert the strongest positive influence on overall competitiveness, while human capital and market position play complementary but statistically significant roles. In particular, digital tools—such as online payments, customer relationship management systems, and service automation—emerge as critical enablers of productivity gains and customer satisfaction in household services. This finding aligns with contemporary service competitiveness theories and reinforces the importance of digital transformation at the local level.

From a methodological perspective, the study contributes by developing a context-specific competitiveness measurement framework that integrates regional statistics, enterprise-level survey data, and spatial analysis. The application of GIS-based visualization further enhances the interpretability of competitiveness patterns and supports evidence-based policymaking. This approach can be replicated in other regions of Uzbekistan or adapted for comparative studies in similar emerging economies.

In practical terms, the results underscore the necessity of strengthening organizational-economic mechanisms through targeted policy interventions. These include promoting digital infrastructure for small service enterprises, expanding vocational training and certification programs, improving access to modern equipment, and fostering fair competition within local service markets. Addressing these factors is essential for narrowing inter-district disparities and ensuring inclusive growth of the household service sector.

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